

An Ene Reaction During Thermolysis of a Benzocyclobutene

TETSUJI KAMETANI, YUICHI SHIRATORI, HITOSHI INOUE,
MASATAKA IHARA and KEIICHIRO FUKUMOTO

Pharmaceutical Institute, Tohoku University, Aobayama, Sendai 980, Japan

and

FUMIO SATOH

The Sendai Institute of Heterocyclic Chemistry, No. 53,
Kawauchi-sanjunin-machi, Sendai 980, Japan

An ene reaction has been observed on thermolysis of 1-(N-allyl-N-benzyl-2-aminoethyl)-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (I). In this paper we also describe the formation of indenenes and indanes from 5-methoxy-1-methyl-1-*p*-toluenesulfonylmethylbenzocyclobutene (VII) by rearrangement.

WE have reported the electrocyclic reaction^{1,2} and inter³- or intra-molecular⁴⁻⁶ cycloaddition reaction of *o*-quinodimethanes generated from benzocyclobutenes with olefins or imines for the synthesis of natural products. In case of benzocyclobutenes which have alkyl substituents at C-1 position and a double bond at an appropriate position in the same molecule, a [1,5] sigmatropic hydrogen migration reaction was observed⁷. During investigation of cycloaddition and [1,5] sigmatropic reaction of benzocyclobutenes, we have found that an ene reaction of an olefin, formed from *o*-quinodimethane by [1,5] sigmatropic reaction, with another olefinic system in the same molecule occurred. Here we wish to report an interesting but unusual reaction of benzocyclobutene chemistry⁷.

When 1-(N-allyl-N-benzyl-2-aminoethyl)-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (I) is subjected to thermolysis an intramolecular cycloaddition reaction would occur; homoazamorphinan (II) or 2-aza-1,2,3,4,4a,9,10,10a-octahydrophenanthrene (III) should be obtained. But if [1,5] sigmatropic reaction would proceed the benzocyclobutene (I) should give olefin (XVI) or C. With this idea in mind, we investigated thermolysis of benzocyclobutenes.

The benzocyclobutene (I) was synthesized from 1-cyano-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (IV)⁸ in seven steps. Hydrolysis of (IV) in ethanolic KOH solution gave the corresponding acid (V) which was converted into (VI) by reduction with LiAlH₄. The tosylate (VII) of the latter was treated with NaCN in anhydrous DMSO to give the nitrile (VIII).

This cyanation using aqueous dimethylsulfoxide gave rise to a ring expansion reaction to afford a mixture of indenenes (IX) and two indanes (X and XI). These structures were assigned by spectral data and chemical reactions (Chart I). After purification by chromatography, the NMR spectrum of the first compound (M⁺160) showed signals at δ 3.48 (4H, *br s*,

2 $\times$ CH₂) and 4.80–5.07 (2H, *m*, >C=CH₂). Therefore, the structure of the first compound was assigned as 6-methoxy-2-methyleneindane (X). The second compound (M⁺160) showed three broad singlets at δ 2.31 (3H, CH₃), 3.20 (2H, CH₂) and 6.30 (1H, —CH)

in its NMR spectrum, but the position of its double bond could not be determined. Ozonolysis of the mixed indene (IX) followed by oxidation of the resultant ozonide gave two carboxylic acids. Multiple recrystallizations of the mixed acids from benzene gave 2-acetylmethyl-4-methoxybenzoic acid (XIV) (M⁺208) as colourless needles, whose structure was assigned by the NMR spectrum showing H-3 at δ 6.70 as a doublet (*J*=2 Hz), H-5 at 6.93 as a doublet-doublet (*J*=8 and 2 Hz) and H-6 at 8.16 as a doublet (*J*=8 Hz). Unfortunately, the second carboxylic acid could not be separated in pure state even by HPLC, but we assigned to it the structure 2-acetylmethyl-5-methoxybenzoic acid (XV) from its NMR spectrum showing the signals at δ 7.03 (2H, H-3 and H-4) and 7.50–7.63 (1H, H-6). Based on the above findings, the indene (IX) was confirmed as a mixture of 5- and 6-methoxy-2-methylindene. The third compound was obtained as an oil; ν_{max} 3600 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 3.30 (1H, *s*, OH); M⁺178. From the spectral data its structure was confirmed as 2-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methylindane (XI).

The cyanide (VIII) was reduced with LiAlH₄ in the presence of AlCl₃ to give the amine (XII) which was converted into the benzylamine (XIII) by condensation with benzaldehyde followed by reduction of the resultant imine with NaBH₄. The secondary amine (XIII) was treated with allyl bromide in the presence of NaHCO₃ to give the desired benzocyclobutene (I).

The benzocyclobutene (I) in toluene was subjected to thermolysis in a sealed tube at 230–235° for 4 hr to afford two olefins (M⁺321 each). One of them, (XVI)

Chart 1

Chart 2

Chart 3

was obtained as a pale yellow oil, whose NMR spectrum showed a toluene-type methyl signal at δ 2.16, a singlet of four methylene protons at 2.50, a doublet ($J=8$ Hz) at 3.03 due to methylene protons of allyl group, a singlet at 3.53 due to benzylic methylene protons, four olefinic protons at 4.83-5.30 as a multiplet and one olefinic proton at 5.50-6.20 as a multiplet. The NMR spectrum of the other olefin (XVII) revealed methyl signal at δ 0.93 as a doublet ($J=7$ Hz), a toluene-type methyl signal at 2.20 as a singlet and two doublets ($J=1$ Hz) at 5.03 and 5.20 due to olefinic protons. Therefore the former (XVI) was formed by only [1,5] sigmatropic reaction of the E-type *o*-quinodimethane (A) and the latter (XVII) from the intermediate (C), which came from the Z-type *o*-quinodimethane (B), by thermal ene reaction.

Thus, we could conclude that an ene reaction proceeded in case of the product formed *via* sigmatropic reaction of 1,1-dialkylated *o*-quinodimethane, in which one substituent has an olefinic system at an appropriate position and it is also found that the geometry of the *o*-quinodimethane controlled whether an ene reaction would proceed or not.

Experimental Procedure

All melting points are uncorrected and were measured with a Yanagimoto melting point apparatus (MS-C2).

IR spectra were taken with a Hitachi 215 spectrophotometer, NMR spectra with a JEOL PMX-60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra with Hitachi RMU-7 and JMX-01SG-2 spectrometers.

5-Methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutenyl-1-carboxylic acid (V)

A mixture of the 1-cyanobenzocyclobutene (IV)⁸ (2.3 g), EtOH (15 ml), KOH (2.3 g) and H₂O (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 18 hr. After removal of EtOH, the resultant aqueous layer was diluted with sat. NaHCO₃ solution (50 ml), washed with Et₂O, acidified with 10% HCl and then extracted with Et₂O. The extract was washed with H₂O, dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to give the carboxylic acid (V), which was recrystallized from benzene to afford colorless prisms (1.72 g, 65.8%), mp 60–62°; IR (CHCl₃): 1700 cm⁻¹ (CO₂H); NMR (CCl₄): 1.67 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.80 (1H, *d*, $J=14$ Hz, H-2), 3.60 (1H, *d*, $J=14$ Hz, H-2), 3.67 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.50–7.10 (3H, *m*, ArH), 9.05 (1H, *b* s, CO₂H) (Found: C, 68.58; H, 6.26. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₃O₃: C, 68.73; H, 6.29).

1-Hydroxymethyl-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (VI)

To a stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (0.5 g) in THF (10 ml) was added dropwise a solution of (V) (1g) in THF (10 ml) under ice-cooling and the stirring was

continued for 3 hr at room temperature. An appropriate amount of 15% NaOH solution was added to the reaction mixture under ice-cooling in order to decompose an excess of LiAlH_4 . The resultant gel was filtered through celite which was washed with Et_2O . The combined layers were evaporated off to leave an oil, which was extracted with Et_2O . The extract was washed with H_2O , dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give (VI) (0.75 g, 80.9%) as an oil. The analytical sample was purified with preparative TLC to afford a colourless oil; IR (CHCl_3) 3600 cm^{-1} (OH); NMR (CCl_4): 1.50 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.03 (1H, s, OH), 2.70 (1H, d, $J=12$ Hz, H-2), 3.03 (1H, d, $J=12$ Hz, H-2), 3.62 (2H, s, CH_2OH), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.53–7.03 (3H, m, ArH) (Found: C, 74.36; H, 7.83. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 74.13; H, 7.92).

5-Methoxy-1-methyl-1-p-toluenesulfonylmethylbenzocyclobutene (VII)

A mixture of (VI) (1.2 g), *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (1.93 g) and pyridine (10 ml) was stirred for 16 hr at room temperature. This was dissolved in benzene (100 ml) and the resultant mixture was washed with sat. KHSO_4 solution and H_2O , dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give the tosylate (VII) (1.97 g, 92.0%) as a yellow oil; IR (CHCl_3): 1350 cm^{-1} (SO_2); NMR (CCl_4): 1.23 (3H, s, C_1-CH_3), 2.43 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.73 (1H, d, $J=14$ Hz, H-2), 3.00 (1H, d, $J=14$ Hz, H-2), 3.63 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.03 (2H, s, CH_2OTs), 6.47 (1H, d, $J=2$ Hz, H-6), 6.60 (1H, dd, $J=8$ and 2 Hz, H-4), 6.86 (1H, d, $J=8$ Hz, H-3), 7.23 (2H, d, $J=9$ Hz, ArH), 7.70 (2H, d, $J=9$ Hz, ArH). This was used for the following reaction without purification because of its instability.

1-(2-Aminoethyl)-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (XII)

A mixture of (VII) (11 g), NaCN (11 g), NaI (11 g) and DMSO (150 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 7 days. This was dissolved in benzene (500 ml) and the resultant mixture was washed five times with H_2O , dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give a brown oil, which was chromatographed on silica gel (200 g) using benzene as eluent to give (VIII) (5.1 g, 76.4%) as a pale brown oil; IR (CHCl_3): 2260 cm^{-1} (CN); NMR (CCl_4): 1.57 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.57 (2H, s, CH_2CN), 2.93 (2H, s, ArCH_2), 3.67 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.67–7.00 (3H, m, ArH).

To a stirred suspension of LiAlH_4 (1.52 g) in Et_2O (10 ml) was added a solution of anhydrous AlCl_3 (5.32 g) in Et_2O (10 ml). After 5 min, a solution of the above nitrile (VIII) (2 g) in Et_2O (10 ml) was added dropwise to the above suspension and the stirring was continued for 2 hr at room temperature. The reaction mixture was treated with H_2O (30 ml) under ice-cooling and then acidified with 6*N* H_2SO_4 (50 ml). The aqueous layer was washed with Et_2O , basified with pellets of NaOH and extracted with Et_2O . The extract was washed with brine, dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give the amine (XII) (1.65 g, 80%) as a yellow oil; IR (CHCl_3): $3500-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH_2); NMR (CCl_4): 1.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.53–2.00 (2H, m,

$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$), 1.80 (2H, s, NH_2), 2.53–3.00 (4H, m, ArCH_2 , CH_2NH_2), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.43–6.93 (3H, m, ArH); MS *m/e*: 191 (M^+). The free base was converted as usual to the hydrochloride, which was recrystallized from $\text{MeOH-Et}_2\text{O}$ to give colourless needles, mp $130-131^\circ$ (Found: C, 62.90; H, 7.98; N, 6.01. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{NOCl}$: C, 63.28; H, 7.97; N, 6.15).

Reaction of (VII) in aqueous DMSO

A mixture of the tosylate (VII) (1.7 g), NaCN (0.5 g), H_2O (10 ml) and DMSO (30 ml) was heated at 55° for 72 hr. The benzene solution of the reaction mixture was washed well with H_2O , dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give a pale green oil, which was chromatographed on silica gel (20 g). The first elution with benzene gave a mixture described later and the second elution with benzene-MeOH (99:1) gave 2-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methylindane (XI) (250 mg, 26.3%); IR (CHCl_3): 3600 cm^{-1} (OH); NMR (CCl_4): 1.37 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.80 (4H, s, $2\times\text{CH}_2$), 3.30 (1H, s, OH), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.30–7.07 (3H, m, ArH); Mass: *m/e* 178 (M^+). Analytical sample was purified by preparative TLC to give a colorless oil (Found: C, 73.67; H, 7.87. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 74.13; H, 7.92).

The mixture mentioned above was subjected to preparative TLC using *n*-hexane. The upper band gave 6-methoxy-2-methyleneindane (X) (20 mg, 2.2%) as an oil; NMR (CCl_4): 3.48 (4H, br s, $2\times\text{CH}_2$), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.80–5.07 (2H, m, $\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 6.27–7.00 (3H, m, ArH), which was easily isomerized to the following indene (IX) on being allowed to stand at room temperature. The lower band gave a mixture of 2-methyl-5- and 6-methoxyindene (IX) as an oil; NMR (CCl_4): 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.20 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.30 (1H, s, CH), 6.50–7.30 (3H, m, ArH); MS; *m/e* 160 (M^+). The structures were confirmed by the following ozonolysis.

Ozonolysis of the indene (IX)

A solution of the indene (IX) (300 mg) in MeOH (10 ml) was ozonolyzed at -78° until the starting material disappeared by TLC. After the reaction mixture was saturated with N_2 , 30% H_2O_2 solution (3 ml) was added to the mixture and the solvent was then evaporated. The resultant mixture was extracted with 10% NaOH and washed with Et_2O . The aqueous layer was acidified with 10% HCl and extracted with Et_2O . The extract was washed with H_2O , dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to give a solid, whose fractional recrystallization from benzene gave 2-acetyl-methyl-4-methoxy benzoic acid (XIV) (60 mg, 15.5%) as colourless needles, mp $143-144^\circ$; IR (CHCl_3): 1710, 1650 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); NMR (CDCl_3): 2.13 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.83 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.70 (1H, d, $J=2$ Hz, H-3), 6.93 (1H, dd, $J=8$ and 2 Hz, H-5), 8.16 (1H, d, $J=8$ Hz, H-6), 9.30 (1H, br s, CO_2H); MS: *m/e* 208 (M^+) (Found: C, 60.75; H, 5.59. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4.0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: C, 60.82; H, 6.03).

Evaporation of the benzene mother liquor during recrystallization gave a solid, which is a mixture of acids (XIV and XV); NMR (CDCl₃): 7.03 (2H, *br s*, H-3 and H-4), 7.50-7.63 (1H, *br s*, H-5) and the same peaks as XIV.

1-(N-Benzyl-2-aminoethyl)-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (XIII)

A solution of the amine (XII) (1.5 g) and benzaldehyde (1.2 g) in methanol was stirred for 2 hr at room temperature and NaBH₄ (3 g) was added to the above reaction mixture under ice-cooling. After the stirring had been continued for 1 hr, MeOH was evaporated to afford a solid, which was treated with H₂O and extracted with benzene. The extract was dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to give an oil, which was converted into the hydrochloride as usual. Recrystallization from MeOH-Et₂O gave colourless needles, mp 175-176° (Found: C, 72.08; H, 7.44; N, 4.07. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₄ONCl: C, 71.78; H, 7.71; N, 4.43).

The hydrochloride was basified with 10% NH₄OH in CHCl₃ to give the amine (XIII) (1.24 g, 56.4%) as a pale yellow oil; NMR (CCl₄): 1.37 (3H, *s*, CH₃), 1.63-2.03 (2H, *m*, CH₂CH₂N), 2.23 (1H, *s*, NH), 2.53-2.93 (4H, *m*, 2×CH₂), 3.63 (3H, *s*, OCH₃), 3.70 (2H, *s*, CH₂Ph), 6.40-6.93 (3H, *m*, ArH), 7.13 (5H, *s*, C₆H₅); Mass *m/e* 281 (M⁺).

1-(N-Allyl-N-benzyl-2-aminoethyl)-5-methoxy-1-methylbenzocyclobutene (I)

A suspension of the hydrochloride of XIII (300 mg), NaHCO₃ (170 mg) and allyl bromide (120 mg) in DMF (10 ml) was stirred at 135° for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with H₂O (12 ml) and extracted with Et₂O. The extract was washed with H₂O, dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to give an oil, which was subjected to chromatography on silica gel (10 g) using benzene as eluent to afford the amine (I) (290 mg, 85.3%) as a yellow oil; NMR (CCl₄): 1.30 (3H, *s*, CH₃), 1.67-2.07 (2H, *m*, CH₂CH₂N), 2.40-2.70 (2H, *m*, CH₂CH₂N), 3.03 (2H, *d*, *J*=6 Hz, CH₂CH=), 3.50 (2H, *s*, CH₂Ph), 3.63 (3H, *s*, OCH₃), 4.90-5.33 (2H, *m*, CH=CH₂), 5.50-6.20 (1H, *m*, CH=CH₂), 6.43 (1H, *d*, *J*=2 Hz, H-6), 6.56 (1H, *dd*, *J*=8 and 2 Hz, H-4), 6.85 (1H, *d*, *J*=8 Hz, H-3), 7.16 (5H, *s*, C₆H₅); Mass *m/e* 321 (M⁺).

This was converted as usual into the oxalate, which was recrystallized from EtOH-Et₂O to give colorless needles, mp 235-236° (Found: C, 69.78; H, 7.24; N, 3.31. Calc. for C₂₂H₂₇NO·C₂H₂O₄: C, 70.05; H, 7.10; N, 3.40).

Thermolysis of (I)

A solution of the amine (I) (100 mg) in toluene (20 ml) was heated in a sealed tube at 230-235° for

4 hr. The reaction mixture was dissolved in 10% HCl and washed with Et₂O. The aqueous layer was basified with 10% NH₄OH and extracted with Et₂O. The extract was washed with H₂O, dried over Na₂SO₄ and evaporated to give an oil, which was subjected to chromatography on silica gel (3 g). Elution with benzene gave N-allyl-N-benzyl-3-(5-methoxy-2-methylphenyl)-3-methylenepropylamine (XVI) (32 mg, 32%) as a pale yellow oil; NMR (CCl₄): 2.16 (3H, *s*, CH₃), 2.50 (4H, *s*, 2×CH₂), 3.03 (2H, *d*, *J*=8 Hz, CH₂CH=), 3.53 (2H, *s*, CH₂Ph), 3.70 (3H, *s*, OCH₃), 4.83-5.30 (4H, *m*, 2×C=CH₂), 5.50-6.20 (1H, *m*, CH=CH₂), 6.46-7.10 (3H, *m*, ArH), 7.17 (5H, *s*, C₆H₅); Mass *m/e* 321 (M⁺).

Elution with benzene-MeOH (99 : 1) gave 1-benzyl-3-methyl-4-[α-methylene-(5-methoxy-2-methylbenzyl)] pyrrolidine (XVII) (23 mg, 23%) as a colourless oil; NMR (CCl₄): 0.93 : (3H, *d*, *J*=7 Hz, CH₃), 2.20 (3H, *s*, CH₃), 3.63 (2H, *s*, CH₂Ph), 3.70 (3H, *s*, OCH₃), 5.03 (1H, *d*, *J*=1 Hz, C=C<H), 5.20 (1, *d*, *J*=1 Hz, C=C<H), 6.43-7.03 (3H, *m*, ArH), 7.20 (5H, *s*, C₆H₅); *m/e* 321 (M⁺).

Both compounds (XVI) and (XVII) were again purified by HPLC (column: Hitachi Gel # 3011, solvent: MeOH, flow rate: 1.5 ml/min) for analytical sample. The former (XVI) was obtained at 9.6 min of retention time and the latter (XVII) at 10 min. High resolution mass spectrum: Found: 321.2091. Calc. for C₂₂H₂₇NO : 321.2094.

References

1. T. KAMETANI, K. OGASAWARA and T. TAKAHASHI, *J. Chem. Soc. Chem. Comm.*, 1972, 675; *Tetrahedron*, 1973, 29, 73.
2. T. KAMETANI, M. KAJIWARA and K. FUKUMOTO, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1973, 1165; *Tetrahedron*, 1974, 30, 1053.
3. T. KAMETANI, M. KAJIWARA, T. TAKAHASHI and K. FUKUMOTO, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I.*, 1975, 737.
4. T. KAMETANI, H. NEMOTO, H. ISHIKAWA, K. SHIROYAMA and K. FUKUMOTO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 3378.
5. T. KAMETANI, Y. KATO, T. HONDA and K. FUKUMOTO, *Heterocycles*, 1976, 4, 241; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 8185.
6. W. OPPOLZER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 1001.
7. I. L. KLUNDT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 70, 471.
8. T. KAMETANI, M. TSUBUKI, Y. SHIRATORI, Y. KATO, H. NEMOTO, M. IHARA, K. FUKUMOTO, F. SATOH and H. INOUE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 42, 2672.